

Three questions to CETAQUA

Interview with Pedro Villanueva Rey, BioReCer project coordinator (CETAQUA)

What is so innovative about BioReCer?

The BioReCer project stands out for its novel approach. While most initiatives focus on the mere use of waste products as feedstock for the production of food, feed and or energy, the BioReCer project goes further aiming to ensure the traceability and environmental performance of biomasses, so they can be used as secondary raw materials for the biobased industry. To do so, it will establish guidelines for current certification schemes to ensure the quality, traceability and sustainability of biomasses. In addition, it will develop a digital platform, which integrates relevant information on biomasses available to all actors involved, promoting the use and transparency.

Where do you see the potential of waste as a valuable resource?

In the current context of climate change, energy and materials supply crisis, the circular economy plays a key role. The reintroduction of waste into the industrial loop significantly reduces the environmental impact derived from the production process, decoupling the use and consumption of resources – in terms of raw materials extraction and waste management – from economic growth thereby.

How can the use of waste feedstock support the EU (bio)economy to become more sustainable and circular?

In the face of the climate crisis and the geo-political situation, Europe and its industry need to become more resilient and independent of external resources. The use of waste as a secondary raw material is an alternative source of renewable and sustainable feedstock, thus favoring the circular economy.

Thanks to the BioReCer project, the hidden value of selected biomasses is recovered by using them to obtain sustainable bioproducts and new synergies are established between biomass producers and the biobased industry on the principles of circular economy and sustainability. Furthermore, the project aims to serve as a basis for the development of new EU policies in the field of waste feedstocks and future certification schemes.